

Organizational Hospital Management Team working as Professional Technological Innovation

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Abstract.

This paper proposes a relation of organizational hospital management team working by hospital management team working superintendence and reviews the organizational hospital management team working planning and performance measurement literature to develop a conceptual model and research propositions. Data are drawn from a survey of the comfort organizations in comfort organizations that around few samples of hospital management team working superintendence engage in organizational hospital management team working. The interview schedule was designed to collect data on a number of hospital management team working superintendence and strategic characteristics in addition to asking about the presence or absence of an organizational hospital management team working and, where appropriate, the time period to which the plan applied. Interviews were conducted face to face directly within the workplace, training and consultant sessions or indirectly by e-mail or using structured questionnaire. It is concluded that hospital management team working superintendence characteristics can be important in explaining and compilation the organizational hospital management team working within the comfort organizations for implementation of organizational hospital management team working planning. In fact, comfort organizations influence whether or not those organizations engage in organizational hospital management team working planning. In this field, the focus is on the special characteristics of hospital management team working superintendence such as education type and level.

Keywords: organizational hospital management team working; hospital management team working superintendence; comfort organizations.

1. Introduction

The hospital management team working superintendence characteristics showing a significant association with a commitment to organizational hospital management team working and also organizational hospital management Team working showed a positive association with that hospital management team working superintendence with a growth orientation. The organizational hospital management team working is production in massive amount with low prices,

which is labeled as economy of scale. Organizational hospital management team working strategy involves adding some new but unrelated products and services to their existing ones and hospital management Team working them to their current customers. This strategy is concerned when a organization tries to increase its control by acquiring organizations that supply it with input or organizations that are customers for its output. It aims at excelling in the competition by offering products with the lowest cost. The focuses are on the relationship between organizational hospital management team working and strategic hospital management team working superintendence. Although development of models appropriate for organizational hospital management team working is appeared to be of requirement, previous researches in this field have rarely taken it into consideration.

Therefore, in the current study, using an organizational hospital management team working, but related fields of study have been combined to each other, and a new model in this field was proposed by employing an exploratory methodology. In organizational hospital management team working strategy a substantial modification of organization and its products are required, i.e., high organizational hospital management team working. These modified products are presented to current customers though the existing channels, thus, there is no fundamental need for the investigation of external environment and affairs, and organization should give priority to taking the internal environment into consideration. A substantial body of research studies has been conducted on organizational hospital management team working and strategy separately. Furthermore, this study provides off the new idea of examining the relationship between organizational hospital management team working and prioritization of internal or external environments. The hospital management team working field is now giving high priority to developing hospital management team working metrics.

Homogenous Diversification strategy: diversification strategy implicates an organization's attempts for adding new but related products and services to its existing ones.

Organizational hospital management team working as professional technological innovation strategy is concerned with maintenance of the status quo. The interdisciplinary conceptual model will provide guidance to hospital management team working managers in developing contextually relevant organizational hospital management team working measures. This study provides hospital management team working managers with specific benefits such as:

- 1) A strategically aligned framework for clearer logic behind actions. More appropriate organizational hospital management team working + hospital management team working superintendence should result in less internal conflict.
- 2) A framework that will provide organizational hospital management team working + hospital management Team working superintendence guidance. In other words, improving one performance measure can adversely affect other performance measures where a comprehensive framework is not used.

The optimization of organizational hospital management team working processes is the most promising strategy when increasing volumes is hard to realize in a saturated market. The hospital management team working increase of would translate into double profit growth for many organizations particularly for organizations competing in a saturated market. Previous literature has also shown that organizational hospital management team working promotion can generate positive cumulative effect on brand choice and purchase quantity and on category incidence. This in return, might lead to having a sustainable competitive advantage on the long run.

Furthermore, comfort organizations spend billions of dollars annually on various forms of advertising to influence current and potential customers to buy their products and services. Moreover, concluded that organizational hospital management team working in the comfort organizations may enhance cash flows, accelerate cash flows, reduce vulnerability in cash flows and increase the residual value of the organization.

The organizational hospital management team working plays an comfort role in understanding the environment by

collecting, disseminating, analyzing and storing information. It includes both a set of functional activities as production, promotion, pricing and distribution and a mind-set that emphasizes the creation of value to alter customer behavior in certain ways. Furthermore, product development process as an important and essential part of innovation. The relative advantages of new products are crucial determinant of accelerated consumer adoption rate and new product success.

2. Hospital management team working

In the organizational hospital management team working, the continuous innovation helps banks to develop new and differentiated offerings in highly homogenized comfort organizations.

It is crucial for comfort organizations to carefully evaluate both their internal capabilities and the external environment, when deciding where to focus their channel innovation efforts. It might be more convenient for some comfort organizations to focus their hospital management team working efforts within the branch channel, while for other comfort organizations it may be more convenient.

A number of customer profiles and their customers' responses to marketing events are used as training data based on which the ways to classify customers into different segments are learnt. A common drawback of inductive hospital management team working is that the training examples may be an incomplete representation of the subject to be learnt and they will lead to an inappropriate conclusion. Organizational hospital management team working feedback technique overcome this problem by using two training sets as positive and negative to correct the wrong conclusion as much as possible. The employee perceived support by top superintendence for organizational hospital management team working and innovation is associated with hospital in superintendence and affective commitment to the organization, as mediated by supervisor support for employee empowerment and development. The authors also concluded that employee perceived support by top superintendence for organizational hospital management team working and innovation is associated with employee perceived service quality and client adherence to their service plan, as mediated by supervisor support for employee empowerment and development, hospital in superintendence and affective commitment to the organization.

Strategic organizational hospital management team working is a new paradigm in the field of organizational hospital management team working, which was under focus of the current study with regard to its role in organizations' development. It is believed the innovation and hospital management team working have a direct effect on organizational presence and the ability of creating a sustainable competitive advantage. hospital management team working superintendence in comfort organizations are responsible for building organizations where people are continually expanding their capabilities to shape their future-that is, hospital management team working managers are responsible for organizational hospital management team working.

The employees who had hospital in their superintendence were performing, cooperating and dedicating their full efforts to the assigned task. The hospital management team working manager's attitudes towards employee involvement were related to unit manager attitudes and to employee attitudes. The top superintendence supports a work climate in which employees may innovate and learn from one another, supervisors will then feel freer to provide greater latitude for employees to make appropriate decisions as well as grow and develop.

This study is based on a sample of small comfort organizations and the influence of organization characteristics such as organizational hospital management team working of organization have been well explored over the last decades. The random sample participated in the survey based on face to face, meeting, advising, questionnaire, participation in consultant sessions and e-mail interviews using a semi structured interview schedule. Hospital management team working managers could answer the key questions about the environmental and strategic variables in which interested and thus the use of a small number of senior managers is not as problematic as it would have been if interested in the psychological and personality characteristics of the hospital management team working superintendence. Hospital

management team working superintendence organization related characteristics were also included to check for the presence of any uncontrolled organization variables. Subsequently, by making connection between elements in the matrix, they can identify their strategy type, and plan to achieve success in current situation, as well as, reaching more desirable situation in the matrix.

3. Hospital management team working

One of the most stable methods of development is hospital management team working strategy. By hospital management team working, products and presenting new or modified products to the market, novel competitive privileges for an organization are created, and if this process continues the organization could easily took the responsibility of the market leadership, and stop being in a passive state. The organizations' need of employing new and powerful techniques in strategy formulation led to investigate corporate organizational hospital management team working status in industrial organizations, as well as whether to give priority to internal or external environments to obtain a stronger model for implementation of industrial organizations. The role of hospital management team working is to implement hospital management team working strategy. Effective organizational hospital management team working is one of the important factors in comfort organizations success as Figure 1.

Figure 1. Hospital management team working strategy

The algebraic sum of outcome obtained from this cooperation is more than the total outcome of those organizations' activities individually. One way to promote comfort organizations development is to offer organizational hospital management team working program in organization that meets the market demands of the productive sectors.

This strategy type emphasizes high corporate organizational hospital management team working, as a result, suggests organizations to encourage hospital management team working, and constantly look for new products and markets, that is, to prioritize external environment to attract new markets with novel attributes. Hospital management team working strategy aims at exploiting the synergy resulted from several organizations' integration for offering some distinct

products cooperatively.

A brief situational analysis of comfort organizations, which indicate that hospital management team working action, is characterized as a practice unless supported by the theory. The reforms to the curricula have been established empirically, organized, distributed and legitimated a hospital management team working discourse limited in its conceptual framework. Establish conceptual basis of analysis to explain the significance to hospital management team working discourse, as an integrator of regulative discourse and instructional discourse and its impact in shaping the hospital management team working models in public accounting programs, which as mediating structures and symbolic message as forms of meaning, inherently reproduce relations of power and principles of specific control. The structure symbolic accounts should be studied dynamically depending on the environment, time and space.

Accounting organizational hospital management team working programs have suffered from a conceptual framework that allows, on strong references, obtaining in the analysis of the different interactions and regulatory mechanisms underlying control, to the discourses, practices, agents and contexts involved in the configuration of hospital management team working discourse and curriculum models.

Hospital management team working superintendence act individually or collectively through professional organizations that allow a special kind of association with different characteristics in relation to commercial comfort organizations. The requirement of compliance with professional standards extends the collective exercise of team the professions are subject to sanctions by professional organizations.

With these elements must be based hospital management team working and professional experience and minimum limits must have a professional to be accepted as professional accountant.

Hospital management team working superintendence generate the general policies, international auditing standards, ethical guidelines, guidelines and organizational hospital management team working and other aspects that are related to the task professional. Moreover, this hospital management team working reduces competition, hereupon; the amount of competitive renovation decreases. Organizations with low organizational hospital management team working have to find ways to create variation in their products.

Further, environmental shifts are so much that the organization has to focus on the external environment primarily. As a result, it decides to cooperate with level organizations to use the obtained shared synergy for overcoming its rivals.

Hospital management team working of the activity scope allows the resources to be concentrated, and obtains a competitive superiority to the rivals. The purpose of focusing on particular products and services is to satisfy the needs of small groups of consumers. Effective factors in organizational hospital management team working strategy include high variety in products, unlimited and indistinct market, unlimited geographical area, unlimited activity, research, and development concentrated on production.

In the case of hospital management team working strategy, products' success, adding more geographical areas or entering other hospital management team working segments such as other layers_of consumer in the same hospital management team working, etc. can raise selling rate. An organization pursuing this strategy, attempts to offer its services and products to new geographical areas. Focusing completely on external environment, the organizations are likely to be able to find new hospital management team working policies for their products. These organizations are regarded as opportunists, which can make double success by using hospital management team working development strategy.

Quality of life, social unity and international responsibility are subject matters of further so-called social indicators of sustainability. These indicators are introduced, their integration into the hospital management team working superintendence system is discussed and the entrepreneurial use demonstrated.

4. Hospital management team working superintendence

The hospital management team working superintendence concept of the hospital management team working development includes superintendence rules, their actors and scopes of action, indicators and objectives as well as a monitoring of the achieved progress and the consequential further adaptation to changing priorities. The present hospital management team working superintendence systems, like as the quality superintendence according, the environmental superintendence or already integrated systems will align themselves with the development in medium term and nurture it. Important actors in organizational hospital management team working process are the comfort organizations. Therefore, hospital management team working superintendence systems have to guarantee a sustained and future-oriented development of the comfort organizations. It is demonstrated how a sustainability hospital management team working superintendence can be incorporated into the operational practice by means of proven systems, like quality and environmental superintendence, by integrating sustainability performances.

Indicators of hospital management team working, like preservation of resources, reduction of the surface consumption and renewable usage of energy but also economic precaution, education and innovation guarantee a high eco-efficiency of operational processes.

Hospital management team working superintendence combining prioritization of internal and external environments with organizational hospital management team working status in one matrix possessed strategic options, from which organizations can choose a proposed strategy according to their organizational hospital management team working intensity and prioritization. Selection of a strategy with respect to a organization's situation, in addition to enabling the organization to develop, and effectively accomplish its goals, could indicate the direction towards higher situations in the matrix.

There is hospital management team working superintendence who argues that formal written planning may be inappropriate for the comfort organizations but this seems a minority view. It can be argued that organizational hospital management team working is as important to comfort organizations as to larger organizations and standard textbooks on entrepreneurship offer chapters on hospital management team working plan whilst a range of specialist publications outline the best ways of writing organizational hospital management team working planning.

A fundamental proposition in hospital management team working strategy is that organizational hospital management team working planning must be aligned with customers and competitive advantage.

Unfortunately, organizational hospital management team working planning performance measurement literature has provided ambiguous guidance to hospital management team working managers.

In comfort organizations, where an organizational hospital management team working planning exists, the preparation of the organizational hospital management team working may have been driven by external forces. The most obvious of these are the requirements of external agencies providing funding for either start up or expansion. However, the organizational hospital management team working planning may serve as a strategic planning document for the managers, entrepreneurs and educated workers, a plan to guide the hospital management team working and serve as a basis for taking strategic decisions and also it may serve as a subsequent monitoring device. In view of its perceived ongoing value to the small business it might be expected that organizational hospital management team working would be a feature of many, if not most, comfort organizations.

In order to achieve hospital management team working success, it is important to understand the relationship between organizational hospital management team working by hospital management team working superintendence and strategy deployment success. As superintendence itself becomes more emphatically fast-paced and intuitive, in order to deal with complexity and unpredictability, research is beginning to accumulate showing that coaching formats used in

superintendence support are more effective than training in the older logical comprehensive pursuits.

Among the strategies, innovativeness was related to the ideal situation and stability referred to the poor condition of a organization. The nature of the hospital management team working superintendence is seen as critical in other aspects of the activities of comfort organizations. A selection of the hospital management team working superintendence characteristics is the potential to influence an owner manager's propensity to undertake organizational hospital management team working.

Predictions of the direction in which the variables (Fegh-hi Farahmand, 2002, 345; Smith, 1967, 145) will operate are inevitably problematic as there is little prior work on the determinants of organizational hospital management team working upon which we can draw (Fegh-hi farahmand, 2005, 37):

- 1) Hospital management team working superintendence ability: This variable has been identified as important in a number of studies.
- 2) Hospital management team working superintendence experience: It may be strongly linked to ability and it could be argued that it might work in two ways. A long number of years running an organization as a hospital management team working superintendence might increase a propensity to plan future directions for the hospital management team working or indeed, once the initial phases had passed and funding secured planning might well be less of a priority.
- 3) Hospital management team working superintendence education level: In the context of organizational hospital management team working, this variable might seem reasonable to hypothesis that the more highly educated hospital management team working superintendence will tend to be more aware of the desirability of organizational hospital management team working and thus, organization run by the better educated hospital management team working superintendence might be more likely to have hospital management team working plans.
- 4) Hospital management team working superintendence hospital management team working: A distinction here may be drawn between those for whom the current organization is their first and serial founders (Bridge, et al, 1998, 124; Chell, 2001, 97; Chell, 1985, 27)
- 5) Hospital management team working superintendence educated workers: This was identified as an influence on organization behavior and in the context of organizational hospital management team working, hospital management team working superintendence with previous work experience in larger organization, perhaps where organizational hospital management team working was seen as an important part of hospital management team working behavior, would tend to encourage organizational hospital management team working in organization.
- 6) Hospital management team working superintendence organizing: Organization founders are drawn either from operatives or from those with previous managerial experience.
- 7) Hospital management team working superintendence strategy: Here it might be argued that hospital management team working superintendence moving into a new sector might be encouraged to plan rather more than those whose businesses were in sectors in which they had considerable prior experience.
- 8) Hospital management team working superintendence potential: This was introduced into the analysis as it might be expected that local hospital management team working superintendence, which grew up in the geographical area under study, will tend to be introspective and less receptive to contemporary superintendence practice.

5. Organizational hospital management team working

The relationships between comfort organizations and their localities have become an important research area and organization with links with local hospital management team working institutions might be more likely to hospital management team working plan. The argument here would be that mixing with local hospital management team

working leaders would increase awareness of the value of organizational hospital management team working.

Further, the characteristics which have been measured can be grouped into environmental and organizational hospital management team working planning variables rather than those variables which measure attributes of the personality of the hospital management team working superintendence.

It is also recognized that the relationships only significant at a relatively low level but this reflects, in part, the small size of our initial sample. Therefore useful conclusions can be drawn as follows:

1) Organizational hospital management team working is a characteristic of the comfort organizations that there still remains a high proportion of hospital management team working superintendence of comfort organizations who does not undertake organizational hospital management team working. Hospital management team working superintendence characteristics and organizational hospital management team working planning variables can be an influence upon whether or not small comfort organizations undertake organizational hospital management team working when controls have been introduced for sector and size.

2) The key hospital management team working superintendence characteristics, associated with a greater tendency to undertake organizational hospital management team working, are a higher level of education level, experience and running hospital management team working.

3) There was no evidence that previous superintendence experience was linked to a higher propensity to hospital management team working plan. That hospital management team working superintendence with superintendence experience is somewhat cynical of the value of paper exercises and the writing of hospital management team working plans.

4) Although this is a study of comfort organizations in one zone, this paper has demonstrated that hospital management team working superintendence characteristics cannot be ignored in trying to understand the extent to which comfort organizations display a commitment to organizational hospital management team working.

6. Success Organizational hospital management team working

Success is most likely to come from policies to that hospital management team working superintendence with the characteristics of planners but who are not yet planners. These are the hospital management team working superintendence that may be unaware of the benefits of organizational hospital management team working rather than outwardly hostile. However, hospital management team working superintendence characteristics are rarely in the public domain so such targeting becomes difficult.

Analysis of the strategic characteristics of hospital management team working superintendence identified a set of variables. Gaining the sustained co-operation of fellow team members requires emotional leadership. Where such leadership is available, much forgiveness is afforded. Performance hospital management team working in a manager links to conceptual hospital management team working. The corporation's key competence, its hospital management team working and industrial concept hospital management team working capability index, is the key to success in a knowledge driven economy. Where creative responses of many kinds are required, managers will prove to be at the heart of superintendence excellence, which empower their colleagues and clients to expand their comfort organizations performance and utilize a higher proportion of the comfort organizations potential.

7. Organizational hospital management team working planning

Comfort organizations to primarily determine their entrepreneurial situation on three levels of low, medium, and high, and then select their prioritization in environmental investigation from the options of focusing on inside the organization, focusing on both inside and outside the organization, and focusing on outside the organization.

Hospital management team working superintendence recent research is reviewing corporate coaching programs that can see this move from intuition towards rationalized models as complementary and off-setting to developments in strategic superintendence.

Like all scientific enterprises, a period of accumulation of evidence will be required before definitive conclusions may be drawn. However, there are early gleanings that evidence based evaluation research is underway as Figure 2.

Figure 2. Organizational hospital management team working planning

Creative hospital management team working building is found in knowledge-based industries, which span many sectors finance, technology, media and learning.

The literature argues shows that the extent to which each determinant of performance impacts firm performance is a function of the performance metrics. Further, define performance as the sum of all processes that will lead managers to taking appropriate actions in the present that will create a performing organization in the future or in other words, doing today what will lead to measured value outcomes tomorrow.

Central to success as knowledge creators is the culturing of independent individuals, organizational members able to reinvent businesses as required. Such capabilities are not nurtured in high compliance systems that penalize out-of-envelope contributions (Fegh-hi farahmand, 2003, 67).

To assist in understanding the process used in a certain application; avoid potential misconceptions regarding the intent and define the activities associated with specific value studies, reclamation has defined four distinct types of organizational hospital management team working's. Also the organizational hospital management team working is a tool to identify key activities that create value and costs in hospital management Team working.

Therefore organizational capability relies in particular on coaching superintendence skills, which rely on emotional intelligence and emphasis one-to-one, dialoguing, subordinate empowerment and mutually agreed targeting. In relation of organizational hospital management team working competencies including outsource less critical resources if better organizational hospital management team working or cost and own competencies core business, three characteristics are competitive advantage and difficult to imitate.

Anyhow tactical actions steps for coupling organizational hospital management team working with customers or service

receivers including to hospital management team working, segment, proposition, and network recovering satisfaction are as follows (Curran, et al, 1994; Fegh-hi farahmand, 2004, 358; Fegh-hi farahmand, 2005, 187; Nayak, et al, 1994, 47; North, et al, 1997, 187):

- 1) Hospital management team working superintendence support: An organization's total professional technological innovation efforts must begin at the very top and begin with the board of directors.
- 2) Hospital management team working superintendence plan: An action plan based on the survey feedback should then be formulated by the top superintendence and communicated at every board meeting.
- 3) Hospital management team working superintendence vision: Develop a vision the organization does not have one already. The key to the initial adoption of professional technological innovation is continuous communication of the vision within a comprehensive communication plan.
- 4) Hospital management team working superintendence improvements: Senior managers need coaching as the new theorists in coaching argue; coaching empowers individuals to achieve their inherent potential.
- 5) Hospital management team working superintendence responsibility: The responsibilities accept of a senior professional technological innovation committee can include: establishing strategic professional technological innovation goals, allocating resources, sanctioning professional technological innovation improvement teams, reviewing key indicators of quality, estimating the cost of poor rescuer, ensuring adequate training of employees and recognizing and rewarding individual and team efforts.

These definitions allow reviewers of a study to professional technological innovation understand its scope and limits. To ensure the opportunity to achieve the highest value, value program staff attempt to keep superintendence or administration directed mission charges flexible enough to allow hospital management Team working. This staff make most of the recommendations for administrative and procurement processes that could benefit from studies (Fegh-hi farahmand, 2009, 97; Steele, 1997, 28-68). Anyhow is the need to develop a means to inform professional technological innovation of the available resources and how to obtain assistance. For this reason, there is a need to re-track fundamental superintendence systems. Such concepts as investment valuation, ethical trading, stakeholder consultation, corporate social responsibility, value investment, preoccupy institutional investor communities. In any case, the level of uncertainty is continuing to increase even as consumer prosperity overlaps into the new century, reacting against the undoubted brilliance of the recent industrial era.

However, the mainly qualitative evidence available to date suggests that organizational hospital management team working planning within comfort organizations is an activity of a minority (Fegh-hi farahmand, 2002, 254). There may be a number of reasons for the lack of organizational hospital management team working planning. Historically the typical hospital management team working superintendence has tended not to have pursued higher levels of education level or to take formal hospital management team working training.

Hence there are two possible reasons why hospital management team working superintendence tends not to plan (Chell, 1991, et al, 167) that they are emotionally unsuited to it. They think and act intuitively and they are simply unaware of the various tools which would enable them to plan systematically. A further constraint, likely to restrict organizational hospital management team working planning by hospital management team working superintendence, is that they may not have sufficient hospital management team working information to prepare a formal plan.

8. Hospital management team working organizations

A lack of formal organizational hospital management team working planning among comfort organizations does not necessarily mean that organization is badly managed. It does, however, suggest that hospital management team working superintendence miss out on the opportunity to consider the overall direction of the hospital management team working

and superintendence decisions may be made on the basis of poor information (Curran, et al, 1994, 39; Fegh-hi farahmand, 2009). The characteristics of the organization and hospital management team working superintendence and also comfort organizations strategies hereafter termed hospital management team working strategy, influencing hospital management team working superintendence behavior which might be used to inform analysis of the determinants of organizational hospital management team working planning in comfort organizations. Organization characteristics were controlled out of analysis in order to focus our attention on the hospital management team working superintendence and organizational hospital management team working planning variables.

With the development of the organizational hospital management team working, the challenges faced by hospital management team working superintendence are larger and larger and the former method. The hospital management team working superintendence should comfort win more customers' favor and obtain more profit resources by the hospital management team working thinking and measures. Through clearing up the correlations between organizational hospital management team working and creating a sustainable competitive advantage, this study has shown the synergistic between both sides and discusses how organizational hospital management team working, professional technological innovation and hospital management team working superintendence can lead to a sustainable competitive advantage.

hospital management team working superintendence in designing and delivering organizational hospital management team working, does not only mean high hospital management team working, but it extends to encompass creativity in the way organizational hospital management team working are delivered through using latest and effective techniques and applications. Frontline employees' skills and abilities may be developed by providing them with the required materials as well as supportive techniques, thus, leading to more hospital management team working strategies in delivering hospital management team working.

Comfort organizations may also present the required facilities to achieve zero-error transactions regarding personal, real estates, or purchasing mortgages, either on the long or short run based on professional technological innovation. It is also important that hospital management team working manager strategic vision and perception of hospital management team working to be in line with creating a sustainable competitive advantage on the long run. Creating an organizational climate encourages, assimilates and promotes hospital management team working, through facilitating team works, offering moral and material incentives and purifying the relationships between all parties in the comfort organizations in question are all central to generate hospital management team working.

Organizational hospital management team working planning does not only depend on acquiring new knowledge, but also on leveraging existing knowledge through knowledge sharing and application within the organization. However, hospital management team working managers should be noted that some managers commented on the concept of hospital management team working by stating that although they are convinced that hospital management Team working in comfort organizations is essential, they face some difficulties in its application.

Some difficulties stems from the gap of understanding and communications between managers at higher and lower level. Other difficulties stems from the weak understanding of how to transfer customer needs into technical specifications. Other stated that the concept of hospital management Team working in its broad definition is understandable; however, when it comes to details, managers face some difficulties on how to reap the ultimate rent out of that hospital management team working.

9. Hospital management team working organizations important

The sustainable competitive advantage stems from the organization ability on retaining and expanding its strategic base through using customer's insight to drive new and novel ideas and dedicate organizational structures and funds to generate hospital management team working. It is not enough for hospital management team working institutions to

have pocket of successful hospital management team working, hospital management team working managers also have to ensure that the efforts are developed and sustained throughout the organization.

Organizational hospital management team working performance and resources allocation should be viewed in favor of long term execution. Hospital management team working organizations should also promote for hospital management team working through presenting some organizational mechanisms that assists in generating new ideas. Hospital management team working organizations may also promote hospital management team working through establishing clear hospital management team working incentives, setting clear targets and metrics for developing and sustaining hospital management team working and systematically providing ways for hospital management team working ideas. Hospital management team working superintendence is a subgroup of customers sharing one or more characteristics that cause them to have similar product needs. Such a classification process is organizational hospital management team working segmentation and marketers may develop a specific marketing strategy for each segment. Providing examples of a particular theme to a learner either human or computer, a conclusion that is as consistent as possible with the training data will be drawn.

Hospital management team working organizations should have both formal and informal hospital management team working structures and based on that, they should be able to identify barriers that hinder them from commercializing hospital management team working. To compete successfully in an organizational hospital management team working, a comfort organization has to know sufficient about the wants and needs of customers but they have different preferences for products and services. It is necessary to classify customers into different segments based on various customer requirements. An inductive organizational hospital management team working to market segmentation will be described. In terms of comfort organizations as a component of the marketing mix, previous research has shown that most organizations have ignored that crucial role of innovative marketing strategies as a tool to create sustainable competitive advantage.

This study informs the hospital management team working manager that hospital management team working strategy should be the primary determinant of an organization's organizational hospital management team working and hospital management team working superintendence framework. It guides the manager in a way that avoids the organizational hospital management team working and hospital management team working superintendence which results in sub-optimization of the performance measurement portfolio.

The positive training set contains example data that are relevant to a hospital management team working theme i.e., relationships between customer attributes and responses to marketing events while the negative training set contains example data that are irrelevant to the same hospital management team working theme.

These different training sets can provide an efficient hospital management team working environment for achieving a more accurate hospital management team working result than only one training set in the traditional inductive hospital management team working method can do. An experiment with real data of customers was performed.

The results show that the inductive hospital management team working and the hospital management team working feedback technique are effective and able to attain high performance of market segmentation. The objective of this study was to evaluate the impact of hospital management team working superintendence in the organizational hospital management team working planning on creating a sustainable competitive advantage. Comfort organizations that undertook more hospital management team working activity, that were more consistent in that activity and whose composition of activity was somewhat differentiated from the industry norm tended to have a sustainable comfort organizations advantage and display superior performance. Hospital management team working activities are undertaken by comfort organizations and which were found to have sustainable competitive advantages. When comfort organizations become more involve with knowledge interaction with their customers during services encounter and

service delivery, they will be more able to understand customer needs and that in return will make organization more innovative.

Organizational hospital management team working in comfort organizations reflects the organization ability to create and expand knowledge through social interaction between both explicit and tacit knowledge, which in this case refers to the knowledge interaction within the organization itself and its clients. Hospital management team working superintendence represents the organization ability to transfer this knowledge into socioeconomic solutions and explains that in order for marketing information to be innovative, organizations are required to have core competences regarding; operating and production capabilities, design, engineering and associated superintendence capabilities and research and development capabilities.

9. Conclusions

Empirical research has shown that organizational hospital management team working does not only depend on acquiring new knowledge, but also on leveraging existing knowledge through knowledge sharing and application within the organization.

The involvement of consumers to support the process of marketing innovations is debatable. The consumers may not be able to specify exactly what they want in the process of developing future products. The consumers lack foresight, since, it is difficult for them to imagine and present ideas regarding something that does not exist and may only make suggestions to improve existing products. Empirical research concluded that the involvement of consumers by need inputs, concept reviews and product tests contributes to the superiority of a product and raise the potential of having a sustainable competitive advantage on the long run. the importance of participation of both research and development and marketing specialists in order to improve consumers' contributions. Such participation and interaction across multiple resources and departments can provide the opportunity for the organization in question to be a market leader in its field. Continuing involvement of consumers with developers in an integrated fashion sustains the melding of consumer needs with technical capabilities.

The comfort organizations may lose their leading position in a given industry, if they fully take the suggestions of their customers into consideration. On the other hand, the involvement of consumers to support the process of marketing innovation and creativity is very well possible.

The consumers need to be encouraged and stimulated to think outside the box and not to limit their ideas to technological possibilities. For hospital management team working managers, the organizational hospital management team working performance measurement is an area that represents a significant opportunity for business investment and superintendence attention.

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